

Intelligent Java Dataset Construction and Visualization Evaluation for Reliable Software Development

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Abstract—As big data and artificial intelligence continue to gain importance, the reliable quality of datasets has become a crucial factor in algorithm performance and result reliability. However, many datasets lack standardization and quality control, which can lead to potential issues in software development and data analysis. In this paper, we propose an objective dataset evaluation algorithm that utilizes multiple metrics, including unified naming conventions and document annotations, for statistical analysis and filtering to ensure reliable data. Our approach scores datasets using reasonable criteria, and we use visualization techniques inspired by remote sensing to compare and visualize reliable dataset quality. Our research demonstrates that our evaluation method is feasible and can assist software developers in enhancing the reliable quality and efficiency of software development by improving dataset quality. Our study concentrates on datasets obtained from GitHub using a web crawler, and our approach establishes a standardized technique for evaluating reliable dataset quality.

Keywords—Python ; GitHub ; Scraping ; Datasets evaluation;

1 Introduction

With the growing importance of big data [1, 2, 3] and artificial intelligence, the quality of datasets has emerged as critical to ensure the robustness and accuracy of learning-based models. In the field of software engineering, intelligent software development methods are gaining popularity among programmers. For instance, many training models based on deep learning have emerged in software method naming [4, 5]. However, extensive practical experience has demonstrated that to obtain powerful models, a strong training dataset is essential as a foundation. If a dataset contains only a small number of examples or has a high degree of noise or bias, it may result in a model that

is not generalizable to new, unseen data, while a well-curated dataset that accurately reflects the language used in real-world software development can help the model learn meaningful patterns and improve its performance. However, existing datasets often suffer from insufficient data quality and coverage [6], limiting the effectiveness of research and development. Furthermore, manually collecting data is often tedious and time-consuming [7, 8] because it requires a significant amount of human effort and resources to gather data from various sources, especially for large-scale datasets. Finally, there is currently a lack of a unified standard for assessing the quality of collected datasets.

To address the problems above, this paper presents an intelligent tool, which can construct high-quality datasets and perform evaluations. The tool, as shown in Figure 1, consists of three main parts.

The first part uses web crawling techniques and the Github API to automatically collect Java datasets from reputable repositories that cover various topics such as object-oriented programming, exception handling, and multi-threading. This part ensures the quality of the collected datasets by sourcing them from reliable repositories. After collecting the dataset, we conducted an analysis of evaluation metrics proposed by some researchers, and ultimately selected the metrics that best reflect the quality of the dataset. These metrics include the quantity of Java methods, the frequency of camel-case method names, the distribution of method name tokens, the number of methods with special prefixes, and whether or not the methods have accompanying documentation comments. The second part uses a variety of metrics to calculate statistical data related to the quality of the dataset. The tool performs data analysis based on these

Figure 1: Java Dataset Construction System and Visualization Evaluation System.

metrics to help users understand the quality of the datasets. Additionally, the tool provides optimization strategies for each metric to help improve the quality of their datasets. The third part of the tool is responsible for evaluating each method in the dataset based on various metric evaluation rules. The tool calculates a weighted sum of the scores obtained for each metric to get the final score for each method. Inspired by remote sensing technologies, a heatmap can be used to reflect the distribution of method quality scores for a given dataset.

In order to meet the needs of users for different data volume levels, we create three Java datasets that consist of a collection of high-quality Java files. These datasets contain over 10,000 Java projects and one million lines of code.

The contributions of this paper can be summarized into three points:

- 1) The tool provides a comprehensive set of metrics to evaluate dataset quality, including Java method quantity, frequency of camel-case method names, distribution of method name tokens, number of methods with special prefixes, and presence of documentation comments. These metrics reflect dataset quality effectively, benefiting practitioners seeking systematic and objective evaluation.
- 2) The tool uses a heatmap to visualize method quality score distribution, inspired by remote sensing technologies. This intuitive visualization helps researchers identify areas for improvement and compare dataset quality easily.
- 3) The tool we introduce not only evaluates but also actively improves dataset quality. It incorporates well-defined metrics and employs filtering processes to

remove undesirable elements. This integration of evaluation and improvement is a novel contribution in the field, surpassing existing tools that solely evaluate dataset quality.

In our experiments, we evaluated three datasets using our intelligent tool and generated heatmap scores based on various evaluation metrics. The comparison of our results with existing evaluation metrics demonstrated the effectiveness of our tool. The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents a survey of related work in the field and positions our work in the context of existing literature. In Section 3, we describe our proposed approach, including the design of our evaluation metrics. Section 4 presents the experiments we conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of our approach. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper with a summary of our contributions and suggestions for future work in this area.

2 Related Work

Datasets are crucial resources in the fields of machine learning and artificial intelligence, and the acquisition and evaluation of datasets have become increasingly important due to the vast availability of diverse data sources through the internet. In this section, we provide a comprehensive overview of the methods for collecting datasets, including potential challenges and solutions. We also introduce the current leading metrics used for evaluating the quality of datasets and how to visualize and analyze the quality of a dataset.

Several previous works have utilized web crawling techniques to collect Java-related datasets. For example, Wu et al. [9] collected hundreds of thousands of lines of Java code by crawling StackOverflow web pages. However, this method has several limitations, such as incomplete or inaccurate data, as well as copyright and privacy issues [10]. In contrast, Alon et al. [11, 12] collected a large-scale Java code dataset, which was used to train a method name generation model. While this dataset has the advantage of a large size, it may not cover all Java application scenarios and coding styles, leading to poor generalization performance. Furthermore, Liu et al. [13] provided the names of high-quality Java dataset repositories but did not offer any tools for crawling these repositories or methods for processing and filtering the crawled data.

To evaluate the quality of datasets, there are many mainstream evaluation metrics available. Code comments have received significant attention from researchers. Zhuo et al. [14] highlighted the importance of code comments and stated that good documentation and code comments are key factors in understanding programs and creating high-quality datasets. Moreover, Sharma et al. [15] analyzed a vast number of databases for code smells and found that the quality of a database is closely related to factors such as the size and popularity of the code repository. In terms of method names,

Metric	Description	Optimization Strategy
Project Quantity	Indicates the level of activity and application of Java development, as well as the size and complexity of Java code.	Exclude empty projects and non-Java projects, retaining only the top 95% of projects ranked by the number of Java files.
Method Naming Quality	Indicates the adherence to naming conventions and readability of methods in Java code.	Exclude method names that do not adhere to the camel case naming convention, do not contain any verbs, and have a number of tokens exceeding 8.
Number of Document Comments	Indicates the quality and coverage of comments in Java code.	Exclude Java files that lack documentation comments.
Proportion of Special Prefix Methods	Indicates the distribution of method body types in Java code.	Count the number of 'get', 'set', and 'is' methods in each Java file, and calculate the percentage of the total number of methods.

Table I: Metrics for Evaluating Java Code Quality.

there are currently several mainstream naming styles. These styles, such as camelCase or underscore, have been subject to debate regarding their superiority. A comprehensive study [16] found that both styles have little difference in cognitive load, although camelCase may have a slight advantage over shorter identifier names. Furthermore, Binkley et al. [17] reported that camelCase style leads to higher accuracy in source code identifier recognition, regardless of whether the participants were programmers or non-programmers. In addition, Reem et al. [18] conducted a large survey with over 1,000 participants, revealing that the majority of method names contain at least one verb and comprise fewer than eight tokens.

In this paper, we propose an approach that allows researchers to input search parameters via a user-friendly GUI, leveraging the advantages of the GitHub official API to improve the efficiency and accuracy of data acquisition. We also employ web crawler acquisition to ensure that our dataset is comprehensive and up-to-date. Furthermore, we use remote sensing techniques to assess the quality of datasets through visualization, which complements existing evaluation metrics. Our approach addresses some of the limitations of previous works, such as incomplete or biased data, and provides a more comprehensive and objective evaluation of datasets. Additionally, our approach can be extended to other domains and applications beyond Java programming.

3 Dataset Evaluation Metric Design

To ensure high quality and suitability of Java datasets, we develop a set of evaluation metrics specifically for assessing their quality. Our proposed metrics are summarized in Table I and measure dataset size, method name and comment quality, and the number of method names with special prefixes. In this section, we provide a detailed description of these metrics and explain how they are combined to create our final scoring rules.

3.1 Project Quantity

In Java development, project and Java file quantification are critical metrics [19]. The number of projects reflects the level of activity and application of Java development in a field, while the number of Java files indicates the scale and complexity of the code. It is crucial to choose large-scale Java datasets for analysis to obtain accurate and precise statistical results. However, some Java projects, like “Javaguide” on GitHub, may not meet our expectations even though they are categorized as Java projects. To address these unique Java projects, filtering them out is critical. We sort the dataset by the number of Java files, and remove projects in the bottom 5% with the least number of Java files. This filtering strategy eliminates empty or non-Java projects, ensuring that only relevant Java projects remain in the dataset.

3.2 Number of Document Comments

In the context of Java programming, document comments play a crucial role in aiding developers to understand the code’s functionality, implementation, and design, ultimately leading to more efficient development and maintenance. Therefore, when evaluating Java datasets, it is important to consider both the quality and quantity of document comments. Good document comments should be clear, accurate, and standardized to ensure seamless communication and understanding among developers. However, poorly written document comments may hinder developers’ comprehension of the code.

To improve the comprehensibility of Java files, we have included the number of document comments as a metric in our evaluation approach. By performing data statistics on Java files that contain document comments and filtering out files without them, we ensure that all Java code in the codebase has sufficient documentation to enhance code readability and maintainability. This approach aligns with

the principles of academic writing and improves the quality of the evaluated dataset.

3.3 Method Naming Quality Metrics

To improve the readability of method names, both industry and academic communities commonly use the camel-case naming convention [20]. This convention involves capitalizing the first letter of each word and concatenating them together, resulting in concise yet expressive method names. For instance, “get_first_name” can be simplified as “getFirstName”. It is also essential to include verbs in method names to convey their purpose and aid in maintenance. For example, “getUserInfo” clearly indicates that the method retrieves user information. Furthermore, the length of method names can impact code quality, with longer names with many tokens being harder to read and understand. As a guideline, method names should not contain more than eight tokens. For instance, “getName” is clearer than “getEmployeeNameByIdAndDepartment”.

To ensure appropriate method naming, we recommend adhering to the following standards:

- Use the camel-case naming style.
- Include at least one verb in the name.
- Limit the number of tokens to eight or fewer.

By following these naming standards, method names can become more descriptive and easier to comprehend.

3.4 Proportion of Special Prefix Methods

When evaluating a Java dataset, it is essential to consider the proportion of special prefix methods such as ‘get’, ‘set’, and ‘is’ methods used to access and set object properties in Java Beans. The appropriate use of special prefix methods can significantly improve code reusability and maintainability. A low count of these methods in a Java dataset can create difficulties for other developers to comprehend object properties and access them, leading to decreased code quality. Additionally, the naming conventions of these methods can significantly impact the associated fields, making them harder to understand. Therefore, it is critical to count the number of special prefix methods in each Java file and calculate their proportion in relation to the total number of methods. This analysis can help identify any potential issues in the dataset’s design and improve the quality of the codebase.

3.5 Scoring Algorithm

This paper presents a scoring algorithm that evaluates the quality of datasets based on four key metrics: camel case naming conventions, presence of a verb in method names, documentation comments, and token count range. To reflect the varying importance of each metric, the algorithm assigns different weights to each one and computes a final score. The detailed algorithm is provided in Algorithm 1. The Dataset Scoring Algorithm is a method for assigning a

score to each method in a dataset based on the four metrics mentioned above. Each metric is assigned a weight (α , β , γ , δ), and the score for each method is calculated as the sum of each metric’s score multiplied by its weight. The resulting score for each method is added to a collection of scores. This algorithm iterates through each method in the dataset and calculates a score for each one, which can be used to quantify the quality level of the methods.

Algorithm 1: Dataset Scoring Algorithm

Input : Dataset
Output: Score collection

- 1 $\alpha \leftarrow$ Weight for camel case method names;
- 2 $\beta \leftarrow$ Weight for method names containing a verb;
- 3 $\gamma \leftarrow$ Weight for documentation;
- 4 $\delta \leftarrow$ Weight for token count;
- 5 $Scores \leftarrow$ empty collection;
- 6 $idx \leftarrow 1$;
- 7 **while** $idx \leq$ number of methods in the dataset **do**
- 8 $Sc \leftarrow$ Score for camel case method names;
- 9 $Sm \leftarrow$ Score for method names containing a verb;
- 10 $Sd \leftarrow$ Score for containing documentation comment;
- 11 $St \leftarrow$ Score for token count;
- 12 $score \leftarrow Sc \times \alpha + Sm \times \beta + Sd \times \gamma + St \times \delta$;
- 13 $Scores.add(score)$;
- 14 $idx \leftarrow idx + 1$;
- 15 **end**
- 16 **return** Scores;

4 Experimental Results

In this section, we describe the methodology used to collect and filter the raw data obtained from GitHub, resulting in three high-quality datasets. The experimental process was divided into three parts: data acquisition, data statistics and dataset scoring.

4.1 Data Acquisition

Data acquisition is a crucial step in the data mining process, as it directly affects the effectiveness of subsequent analysis and mining. We utilized the GitHub API to directly collect a large amount of repository data from the platform without the need for manual search and download. Using the API ensured compliance with the usage rules of the platform and avoided any legal risks.

To collect the data, we used the Python programming language and two Python libraries: PyGithub and GitPython. PyGithub provided a simple and easy-to-use interface for accessing the GitHub API, while GitPython helped us manipulate the Git version control system, including cloning code libraries from remote repositories, pushing code to

Figure 2: GUI tool.

remote repositories, etc. By combining these two libraries, we efficiently obtained repository data from GitHub and downloaded code repositories locally for subsequent analysis.

We used a GUI interface to easily crawl data (Figure 2). Users entered parameters like programming language, number of repositories, and star range. After clicking “Start Crawling”, users chose a local path to save the repository. The tool created a folder in the specified path, saved the crawled repository, and recorded repository information in a txt file. It connected to the GitHub API, searched for repositories meeting the criteria, downloaded the code, and displayed the number of successfully crawled repositories.

We crawled three different-sized datasets, JDataMineSmall, JDataMineMid, and JDataMineLarge. These datasets contained repositories with more than 500 stars.

4.2 Data Analysis

This study conducts statistical analysis on three Java datasets using four metrics: project count, method name quality, document comment count, and proportion of special prefix methods.

4.2.1 Counting Java File Numbers in Different-Scale Projects

Dataset	Number of Projects	Number of Java Files
JDataMineSmall	151	17,382
JDataMineMid	301	86,526
JDataMineLarge	425	231,065

Table II: Number of Projects and Java Files in Three Datasets.

To evaluate the effectiveness of our method on Java projects with different scales and complexities, we counted

Figure 3: Method Name Token Count Distribution.

the number of Java files in each project and presented the results in Table II. The table reveals the following findings:

- The JDataMineLarge dataset comprises the highest number of Java files, with 231,065 files, followed by JDataMineMid with 86,526 files, whereas JDataMineSmall has the lowest number of files with only 17,382.
- A positive correlation exists between the number of Java projects and the number of Java files in each dataset. For instance, the JDataMineSmall dataset exhibits an average of 115 Java files per project, whereas the JDataMineLarge dataset has an average of 544 Java files per project.

4.2.2 Counting the Number of Valid Method Names

The experiment examines method naming styles in three code repositories (JDataMineSmall, JDataMineMid, and JDataMineLarge), focusing on camelCase and verbs in method names. We analyze the distribution of method names based on token count.

Table III shows statistics for camelCase method names and verb-containing method names in the repositories. Both increase with repository size. CamelCase names significantly outnumber non-camelCase names, indicating its dominance. The difference between verb-containing and camelCase names is small, suggesting a relatively high occurrence rate for verb-containing names.

We also study method name distribution by token count. Figure 3 reveals two-token names as most common across all datasets, while names with eight or more tokens are rare. Programmers prefer clear and concise method names over verbose and complex styles.

4.2.3 Counting the Number of Java Files with Effective Documentation Comments

In this study, we analyzed the prevalence of effective documentation comments in three Java datasets: JDataMineSmall, JDataMineMid, and JDataMineLarge. Effective documentation comments in Java codebases are defined as comments that begin with either the `/**` or `/*` syntax and contain at least one non-empty line. Single-line comments starting with `/**` are excluded from this analysis.

Dataset	Camel Case	Not Camel Case	Method Names with Verbs	Method Names without Verbs
JDataMineSmall	133,333	6,517	128,728	11,122
JDataMineMid	685,488	52,511	672,530	65,469
JDataMineLarge	1,887,037	78,477	1,772,431	193,083

Table III: Metrics for Evaluating Method Naming Conventions in Three Java Code Repositories.

Our results, as shown in Table IV, demonstrate that effective documentation comments are commonly found in Java projects. Specifically, 60.7%, 65.5%, and 82.0% of the analyzed Java files in JDataMineSmall, JDataMineMid, and JDataMineLarge, respectively, contain such comments.

Dataset	Files with Documentation	Percentage
JDataMineSmall	10,558	60.7%
JDataMineMid	56,669	65.5%
JDataMineLarge	189,534	82.0%

Table IV: Number of Java Files with Effective Documentation Comments in Codebases.

4.2.4 Analysis of Method Name Prefixes in Three Java Codebases

The purpose of this study was to investigate the frequency of method names starting with the prefixes ‘get’, ‘set’, and ‘is’ in the three Java codebases. The results, as presented in Figure 4, reveal that ‘get’ methods were the most commonly used prefix in all three codebases. In JDataMineSmall, 18.7% of method names started with ‘get’, while in JDataMineMid and JDataMineLarge, the proportions were 20.6% and 20.4%, respectively. The ‘set’ prefix was the second most frequently used prefix, with proportions of 10.6% in JDataMineSmall, 8.9% in JDataMineMid, and 12.0% in JDataMineLarge. Finally, the ‘is’ prefix was the least common, with proportions of 3.3%, 3.7%, and 3.8% in JDataMineSmall, JDataMineMid, and JDataMineLarge, respectively.

These findings suggest that developers tend to favor ‘get’ methods for retrieving information from objects. Moreover, the results have practical implications for heuristic method name recommendation approaches. For instance, recommendation tools could prioritize ‘get’ prefixes when suggesting method names for developers, as they are the most frequently used prefix across all three codebases.

4.3 Scoring and Comparison of Datasets

We evaluated the effectiveness of our dataset scoring algorithm 1 using the discussed evaluation metrics and algorithm. To enhance its performance, we introduced additional details and heatmaps inspired by remote sensing. The parameter settings used in the experiments were as follows:

Figure 4: Proportions of Special Prefix Methods.

- The weight for camel case method names is 20%. Methods that are not in camel case receive a score of 5, while those that are in camel case receive a score of 10.
- The weight for method names containing a verb is 10%. Methods that do not contain a verb receive a score of 3, while those that do contain a verb receive a score of 10.
- We assign a weight of 30% to documentation. If a method in a Java file has documentation, it receives a score of 10. Otherwise, it receives a score of 8.
- The weight for token count is 40%. Methods that have a token count outside 5 receive a score of 2. Methods with a token count in the range of 2-3 receive a score of 10, while those with a token count in the range of 1, 4, or 5 receive a score of 6.

Weights were assigned based on initial exploratory analysis and expert judgment. For example, we assigned a weight of 20% to camel case method names and 10% to method names containing a verb, considering their importance in dataset quality. These weights may not be perfect and can be further refined through future rigorous statistical analysis. To visualize the quality of dataset methods, we propose a heatmap-based method using our scoring algorithm 1. Java methods in the dataset were categorized into 676 groups based on their first and last letters (a to z). The heatmap

represents these categories, with the x-axis indicating the first letter and the y-axis indicating the last letter of method names. Method names not ending with a letter were excluded. Each heatmap cell represents the average score of methods in that category, with color indicating method name quality. Red indicates higher scores, while blue indicates lower scores. Deep blue areas with a score of 0 represent categories without methods, not poor-quality method names.

As shown in Figure 5, before optimizing the jDataMineSmall dataset, most heatmap cells were light red, indicating that most methods had an average score between 6 and 8. To optimize the dataset, we applied the algorithm described in Section 3. First, we filtered out methods with non-camel case naming conventions to ensure compliance with international standards. Second, we removed Java files without documentation comments to improve code readability. Third, we excluded methods that do not contain verb names to improve semantic accuracy. Finally, we filtered out methods with more than 8 tokens to obtain concise and informative method names.

Figure 5: Heatmap of The Unprocessed JDataMineSmall Dataset.

Our heatmap-based method allows for effective dataset comparison and evaluation in the field of artificial intelligence. We have developed a tool that optimizes dataset quality based on specific evaluation metrics. For example, our tool filters out Java methods that do not adhere to camel case naming conventions, as we believe this reflects good coding practices and contributes to dataset quality. Similarly, methods without documentation comments and those lacking verbs in their names are also excluded. By implementing these filtering processes, we ensure that the resulting datasets are of high quality and can be relied upon for further analysis. This work establishes a foundation for the development

Figure 6: Heatmap of The Processed JDataMineSmall Dataset.

of new large language models in software engineering. The datasets and experiment scripts can be found in our GitHub repository at <https://github.com/lidiancracy/JDataMine>.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper, we propose an algorithm for evaluating Java datasets that utilizes statistical analysis and filtering techniques. We applied this algorithm to collect Java datasets through web crawling and the GitHub API, and generated a heatmap that considers various metrics. Our research has demonstrated the effectiveness of the data collection method used, providing a reliable and comprehensive dataset, as well as the ability to intuitively compare the quality of different datasets.

However, there remain limitations and opportunities for further research. Future studies could consider using additional metrics to assess the quality of Java methods, such as the consistency between method names and bodies, method execution time, and other factors. We can also explore more sophisticated filtering methods, such as eliminating low-quality code, to enhance dataset quality. Additionally, combining heatmap scores with machine learning techniques to detect patterns and anomalies in code can help to further investigate quality issues related to Java methods.

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